

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF BIGUANIDE WITH TERVALENT METALS. PART IX. ACTION OF MERCURIC CHLORIDE AND SILVER NITRATE UPON CHROMIUM AND COBALTIC TRISBIGUANIDIUM HYDROXIDES AND THE CONSTITUTION OF BIGUANIDE METAL COMPLEXES.

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According to the constitution suggested for the biguanide metal complexes in a previous communication of the series it was expected that the complex metal biguanide bases should behave like ammonia or the amines. An additional evidence in this respect has been brought forward in this paper by a study of the behaviour of these complex bases towards mercuric chloride and silver nitrate. By adding mercuric chloride to chromium and cobaltic trisbiguanide bases, the compounds $\text{Cr}(\text{Big}\cdot\text{HgCl})_3$ and $\text{Co}(\text{Big}\cdot\text{HgCl})_3\cdot\text{HgCl}_2$ were obtained, which closely resemble the infusible white precipitate in their constitution and properties. It has also been shown that with AgNO_3 the cobaltic trisbiguanide hydroxide forms the compound, $\text{Co}(\text{BigH}\cdot\text{AgOH})_3$, aq., resembling silver ammine hydroxide.

Two more compounds of mercuric chloride with biguanide and ethylenediamine hydroxide, $\text{CH}_2\text{NH}\cdot\text{C}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{C}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{HgCl}$ and a $\left[\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_2\text{NH}\cdot\text{HgCl} \\ | \\ \text{CH}_2\text{NH}\cdot\text{HgCl} \end{array} \right] \cdot \text{HgCl}_2, 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ respectively, also of the infusible white precipitate type, have been described.

Besides, double salts of the composition, $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}_2)_3]\text{Cl}_3\cdot 3\text{HgCl}_2$; $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}_2)_3]\text{Cl}_3\cdot 3\text{HgCl}_2\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3]\text{Cl}_3\cdot 5\text{HgCl}_2\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (in two different crystalline forms and colour) have been prepared and their properties studied.

A detailed discussion regarding the constitution of metal biguanide complexes was made in the first paper of the series and a structure based on their chemical and physical properties was also suggested (Rây and Saha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 670). It was shown that three biguanide molecules, functioning as bidentate or double-bonding groups, co-ordinate with each metal atom (Cr^{3+} or Co^{3+}) to form an inner metallic complex with one of the end-amino groups of each biguanide molecule remaining free for further co-ordination or salt formation. This makes the complex as a whole a trivalent cation, representing an inner metallic complex of the second order. The central atoms, Cr or Co, have their primary valencies fully saturated by displacing a hydrogen atom of one of the imino groups ($=\text{NH}$) of each biguanide molecule and cannot, therefore, make any contribution towards the electrical character of the complex ion. Chromium

and cobaltic *tris*biguanidines, therefore, should behave in aqueous solution to a certain extent like ammonia or the organic amines, and, like the latter, combine with mercuric chloride to form insoluble compounds of the "infusible white precipitate" type. Similarly, with silver nitrate, compounds of the silver ammine type are to be expected. These have actually been verified by experiments as described in this paper.

Free biguanide hydroxide or free ethylenediamine hydrate have been found to react with mercuric chloride to give compounds, resembling infusible white precipitate of the following types :

Biguanide is also closely related to biuret and dicyandiamidine :

and it has further been observed that the dicyandiamidine base does not give with mercuric chloride a precipitate of HgO, but a very light yellow insoluble compound of the infusible white precipitate type. Mercuric compounds of biuret of the type $\text{Hg}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)_2 \cdot 2\text{HgO}$ have already been described by Schiff (*Ber.*, 1896, 29, 299 ; *Annalen*, 1898, 299, 242). Even the pure carbamide like urea, in presence of NaHCO_3 , gives a large number of mercuric derivatives of the infusible white precipitate type which can be represented as

the infusible white precipitate type. Addition of HgCl_2 to $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3](\text{OH})_3$, gave a bright yellow precipitate which changed within a few minutes into a brown oxychloride, $2\text{HgO} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$, even in the cold.

However, a few unstable compounds, somewhat analogous to the infusible white precipitate, have been described by Vortmann and Morgulis (*Ber.*, 1889, 22, 2644). These were obtained by the addition of HgCl_2 solution to that of different cobaltamine chlorides in presence of varying amounts of NaOH . It was assumed by the authors that the substitution of an H-atom of ammonia by HgCl or HgOH radical takes place here even when the ammonia molecule is co-ordinated with the metal atom. It is, however, noteworthy that except in a few cases the analytical results show a considerable deviation from those of the formulac proposed. All these compounds again are unstable and readily break down with dissolution of the complex into a black mass. As the reactions were carried out in solutions rendered strongly alkaline with caustic soda, decomposition of the cobaltamines with liberation of ammonia is not excluded here. It might also happen that the co-ordinated NH_3 molecules exhibit some differences from co-ordinated $-\text{NH}_2$ groups, when reacting with HgCl_2 .

The mercuric chloride derivative of the complex chromium biguanide base was obtained in two different forms: one, the anhydrous, the other as a monohydrate. These differed in their colours. As both the hydrated and the anhydrous varieties were equally stable under ordinary conditions, it seems to suggest a metastable state for the hydrated variety, if, of course, the possibility of space-isomerism due to difference in the position of HgCl groups in the molecule, as shown below, be excluded. The hydrated variety has been found to change into the anhydrous form by prolonged boiling with water.

The dot with the bar (symbol) indicates the position of HgCl group.

Attempts to prepare compounds of the metallic biguanide bases with Nessler's reagent have not been successful. Insoluble brown precipitates

of variable composition were obtained when the complex bases were treated with K_2HgI_4 .

The free metal biguanide base like ammonia may be regarded as an equilibrium mixture of the following :

Mercuric chloride reacts with the anhydrous basic $M(\text{BigH})_3$ as with NH_3 .

The silver salts combine with ammonia and organic amines to give, as is well known, the complex silver amines, where the silver atom occurs generally in twofold co-ordination with ammonia or the amines. Silver compounds of guanidine, biuret and urea, having the compositions $\text{Ag}(\text{CN}_2\text{H}_3)\text{NO}_3$, $\text{Ag}_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}_3\text{O}_2)$, $\text{Ag}_2(\text{CON}_2\text{H}_2)$ have been described (Hofmann, *Ber.*, 1868, 1, 146; Wisliscenus, Bouue and Goldenberg, *Ber.*, 1874, 7, 287; Mulder, *ibid.*, 1873, 6, 1019). The latter two are regarded as simple salts in which biuret and urea behave as disbasic acids.

By adding silver nitrate to the free biguanide base, no Ag_2O but a white insoluble voluminous precipitate, soluble in ammonia was obtained. This on analysis, however, gave no definite stoichiometric composition.

It was expected that the complex metallic biguanide bases should give with silver oxide compounds analogous to the silver ammine hydroxides. In fact by adding silver nitrate to cobaltic biguanide hydroxide, no silver oxide, but, on the contrary, a pinkish precipitate of the composition, $\text{Co}(\text{BigH}.\text{AgOH})_3.\text{aq}$, was produced (BigH_2 =one biguanide molecule). The compound, however, is not very stable. In this connection it may be mentioned that cobaltamine hydroxide or cobaltic ethylenediamine hydroxide, in which all the NH_2 molecules or $\cdot\text{NH}_2$ groups are co-ordinated to the central cobalt atom and have got no more lone pairs of electrons, gives a precipitate of Ag_2O when treated with AgNO_3 . In fact these complex hydroxides can be prepared in the pure state by treating the corresponding chloride with silver oxide.

Co-ordination of the silver ion with any of the $=\text{NH}$ groups in the biguanide molecules is highly improbable, since no silver imine complex is known. Silver succinimide,

1872, 162, 168), may be regarded as a simple salt of silver, formed by the displacement of the H atom of the $=\text{NH}$ group of the succinimide molecule. All compounds, such as biuret, urea and succinimide, in which one or more hydrogen atoms are replaced by silver to form salt-like compounds, are characterised by having carbonyl ($-\text{CO}-$) groups in the molecule. But no

amidine of the type $R-C \begin{matrix} \diagup NH \\ \diagdown NH_2 \end{matrix}$ is known to form salt-like compounds with silver; with guanidine, on the other hand, it forms an addition complex, as already stated (Hofmann, *loc. cit.*). The only remaining possibility of the linking of Ag^+ or $AgOH$ with an already co-ordinated biguanide molecule is through the free $-NH_2$ group, not co-ordinated to the central cobalt atom. The probable structure of the compound under discussion is, therefore, given by :

This is comparable to monamine silver hydroxide ; the large volume of the co-ordinating cobalt-biguanide group probably reduces the co-ordination number of silver, if we assume the hydroxyl group to be ionisable. Alternatively, it may be regarded as a nonionisable compound with co-ordination number of silver equal to 2 as usual.

On adding silver nitrate to chromium biguanide base, no Ag_2O , but a pinkish precipitate having no definite composition was produced. This may be due to the partial hydrolysis of chromium *trisbiguanide* base in aqueous solutions into chromium hydroxo-aquo-*bisbiguanide* base and free biguanide (Rây and Saha, *loc. cit.*).

The formation of the above described mercury and silver derivatives of cobalt and chromium *trisbiguanide* bases furnishes additional evidence in support of the constitution of the biguanide metal complexes suggested by Rây and his co-workers (*loc. cit.*), showing that free metal biguanide bases behave like ammonium hydroxide in aqueous solution :

where $M = Cr^{3+}$ or Co^{3+} .

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Chromium trisBiguanide Mercuri-chloride.—A solution of freshly prepared and recrystallised chromium *trisbiguanide* monohydrate was warmed on the water-bath and an excess of a solution of $HgCl_2$ in a large volume of water was added to it, drop by drop, with constant stirring ; the

resulting light violet precipitate was filtered and washed first with cold water and then with alcohol. The substance was dried over concentrated H_2SO_4 for 12 hours and then kept exposed to air until it attained a constant weight. [Found: N, 19'51; Cl, 10'09; Cr, 4'83; Hg, 56'46. Cr(Big.HgCl)₃ requires N, 19'87; Cl, 10'07; Cr, 4'92; Hg, 56'94 per cent].

The substance is insoluble in water or solutions of alkali (dil. or conc.), but soluble in dilute mineral acids. On prolonged boiling with strong alkali solutions it suffers slow decomposition.

A rose-red monohydrated derivative of the above compound was obtained when the precipitation was carried out in ice-cold solution. {Found: Cl, 9'84; Cr, 4'67; Hg, 55'88. Cr(Big.HgCl)₃.H₂O requires Cl, 9'89; Cr, 4'83; Hg, 55'98 per cent}.

Double Compound of Cobaltic trisBiguanide Mercuri-chloride with Mercuric Chloride.—A solution of freshly recrystallised cobaltic biguanide hydrate (Ray and Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 621) was heated on a water-bath and an excess of a solution of $HgCl_2$ in a large volume of water was added to it, drop by drop, with constant stirring. A dull red precipitate appeared; it was filtered hot and washed with water. The product was dried over sulphuric acid in vacuum and then kept exposed to air until it attained a constant weight. [Found: N, 15'70; Cl, 13'23; Co, 4'48; Hg, 60'17. Co(Big.HgCl)₃.HgCl₂ requires N, 15'72; Cl, 13'24; Co, 4'41; Hg, 60'08 per cent].

The substance is insoluble in water and alkalis, slightly soluble in alcohol but dissolves readily in mineral acids.

Biguanide Mercuric Chloride.—A solution of biguanide hydroxide, prepared from biguanide sulphate and barium hydrate, was cooled and treated with an excess of cold $HgCl_2$ solution, and added drop by drop with vigorous stirring, when a flocculent precipitate appeared. This was washed with cold water and dried over concentrated H_2SO_4 in vacuum and afterwards exposed to air till its weight became constant. [Found: N, 12'26; Cl, 12'37; Hg, 69'71. (ClHg)—NH—C—NH—C—NH(HgCl)
 $\begin{array}{c} || \qquad \qquad || \\ NH \qquad \qquad NH \end{array}$

requires N, 12'27; Cl, 12'41; Hg, 70'25 per cent].

The substance is insoluble in water, alcohol or alkaline solutions, but soluble in mineral acids.

Compound of Ethylenediamine with Mercuric Chloride.—Several compounds of ethylenediamine with mercuric salts have been described by Scherring ("Chemische Fabrik auf Aktein," Berlin, 1901). He prepared a compound from mercuric chloride and ethylenediamine (m.p. 180°) in the form of white needles, insoluble in water or alcohol, but soluble in

excess of ethylenediamine. Detailed studies as to its formula and constitution do not, however, appear to have been made. It has been observed by us that by adding mercuric chloride solution to ethylenediamine in different proportions or *vice versa* under different conditions, mixtures of various compositions were obtained. A pure compound can, however, be prepared by the following process.

A very dilute solution of ethylenediamine was added, drop by drop, to large excess of a concentrated solution of mercuric chloride with vigorous stirring at the room temperature. A voluminous white precipitate was formed. This was washed with cold water several times, dried in vacuum over sulphuric acid for twelve hours and then exposed to air till it attained a constant weight. {Found: N, 3·84; Cl, 14·63; Hg, 68·96. $2 \left[\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_2\text{NH}\cdot\text{HgCl} \\ | \\ \text{CH}_2\text{NH}\cdot\text{HgCl} \end{array} \right] \text{HgCl}_2, 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 3·84; Cl, 14·58; Hg, 68·8 per cent}.

The substance is slightly soluble in hot water and the solution deposits mercury on a piece of clean strip of copper dipped into it.

Double Compound of Chromium trisBiguanide Chloride with Mercuric Chloride.—To an ice-cold solution of chromium trisbiguanide hydrochloride (Rây and Saha, *loc. cit.*) a cold solution of mercuric chloride in excess was added, drop by drop, with stirring. The solution, on keeping in the cold, gave a crop of beautiful orange red crystals. These were washed with cold water and dried in air. {Found: Cl, 25·03; Cr, 4·04; Hg, 47·07. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}_2)_3]\text{Cl}_3\cdot 3\text{HgCl}_2$ requires Cl, 25·0; Cr, 4·08; Hg, 47·17 per cent}.

The substance is soluble in water and alcohol.

Double Compound of Cobaltic trisBiguanide Chloride with Mercuric Chloride.—To an ice-cold solution of cobaltic trisbiguanide hydrochloride (Rây and Dutt, *loc. cit.*) was added a solution of mercuric chloride in excess and the mixture was stirred for a few minutes, when a crop of beautiful brownish yellow crystals appeared. These were washed with cold water and dried in air. {Found: Cl, 24·35; Co, 4·49; Hg, 45·61. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}_2)_3]\text{Cl}_3\cdot 3\text{HgCl}_2\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cl, 24·19; Co, 4·47; Hg, 45·63 per cent}.

The substance is readily soluble in water and more so in alcohol.

Double Compound of Ethylenediamine Cobaltic Chloride and Mercuric Chloride.—A solution of trisethylenediamine cobaltic hydroxide, prepared from its chloride and moist silver oxide, was treated with a concentrated solution of mercuric chloride in excess. A yellow precipitate (A) appeared, which on warming changed readily into a brown-red insoluble substance (B). This was washed with hot water and dried over sulphuric acid in

vacuo. The hot filtrate gradually deposited fine, golden yellow plates of a third substance (C), which were washed with ice-cold water and dried in air.

The substance (A) was very unstable and changed even at 0° readily into (B).

[Found (substance B) : Cl, 10.02; Hg, 85.27. $2\text{HgO} \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$ requires Cl, 10.07; Hg, 85.38 per cent].

The compound (C) gave on analysis : Cl, 26.68; Hg, 57.86; Co, 3.47. $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 5\text{HgCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cl, 26.51; Hg, 57.68; Co, 3.39 per cent. (en = one molecule of ethylenediamine). The compound (C) is readily soluble in water and alcohol.

A compound of the same composition as (C), but of a different colour and crystalline appearance, was prepared by keeping a solution of mercuric chloride mixed with that of *tris*ethylenediamine cobaltic chloride in the cold for sometime. The orange-yellow needles, which separated out, were washed with cold water and dried in air. This substance (D), like (C), was also readily soluble in water and more so in alcohol. It gave on analysis Cl, 26.56; Co, 3.41; Hg, 58.08 per cent. Its crystals appeared as hexagonal orange prisms under the microscope. It can, therefore, be concluded that the double salt $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 5\text{HgCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is dimorphous. The orange-yellow variety is the stable form at lower temperature and changes into the golden yellow plates at higher temperature.

Cobaltic Biguanide Silver Hydroxide.—A solution of silver nitrate was added with stirring to an ice-cold solution of cobaltic *tris*biguanide hydrate (Ray and Dutt, *loc. cit.*). The resulting precipitate was washed with ice-cold water till free from nitrate. This was dried over H_2SO_4 in *vacuo* for 12 hours. On keeping for a longer period over sulphuric acid the substance partially loses weight and suffers gradual decomposition.

It gave on analysis N, 23.74; Ag, 37.0; Co, 6.52 per cent. Hence Ag : Co : N = 3 : 1 : 15. This corresponds to $\text{Co}(\text{BigH} \cdot \text{AgOH})_3$, aq. where $\text{BigH} = \text{C}_2\text{N}_3\text{H}_8$.

The substance forms pink coloured powder and decomposes on boiling in aqueous suspension. It reacts alkaline and readily dissolves in acids. With concentrated ammonia it forms silver ammine hydroxide and cobaltic *tris*biguanide base. Thus,

